

Acta Medica Europa

Satisfaction and Expectance about MRI Experiences: A Questionnaire-Based Study

Amir Gupta ¹, Payel Khan ²

¹ Department of Radiology, New Delhi Hospital, New Delhi, India

Article Info

Received: 5 September 2022

Accepted: 10 September 2022

Published: 11 September 2022

Keywords:

Magnetic resonance imaging, patient satisfaction, patient expectations, patient experience, questionnaire study.

Corresponding author:

Amir Gupta.

Department of Radiology, New Delhi Hospital, New Delhi, India

dramirgupta@inbox.lv

ABSTRACT

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a commonly utilized diagnostic tool, yet patient satisfaction and expectations regarding the experience can vary greatly. This study aimed to assess patient satisfaction and expectations related to different aspects of the MRI experience, identify factors influencing satisfaction, and compare patients' pre- and post-examination expectations. A cross-sectional study was conducted at a secondary care hospital in India. Two hundred consecutive patients undergoing MRI examinations were invited to participate. A self-administered questionnaire assessed pre-examination expectations regarding information provision, wait times, procedure explanation, and pain management. After the examination, participants completed a satisfaction questionnaire evaluating the same aspects, along with perceived quality of care and overall satisfaction. The mean overall satisfaction score was 4.12 (out of 5), with information provision having the highest satisfaction (4.25) and wait times the lowest (3.87). Significant differences were observed between pre- and post-examination expectations for all aspects except quality of care, suggesting that the actual experience influenced how patients perceived various aspects of the MRI procedure. Factors like clear explanation of the procedure, shorter wait times, and effective pain management were significantly associated with higher satisfaction. Our findings highlight the importance of comprehensive pre-examination information, minimizing wait times, and effective pain management for improving patient satisfaction with MRI experiences. Addressing unmet expectations through enhanced communication and patient-centered care can further improve satisfaction and reduce anxiety associated with MRIs.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10444951

INTRODUCTION

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has revolutionized medical diagnostics, offering intricate glimpses into the human body's hidden landscapes. Yet, while its technological marvels illuminate disease, the patient experience within the MRI scanner can be shrouded in shadows of anxiety, uncertainty, and discomfort. Stepping into this metallic labyrinth, patients often grapple with a symphony of emotions: curiosity about the impending examination, apprehension about the unfamiliar procedure, and concern about potential pain or discomfort (1-4).

Understanding and addressing these emotions lies at the heart of patient-centered care. Patient satisfaction with MRI experiences is not merely a measure of service quality; it significantly impacts clinical outcomes by influencing patient adherence to treatment plans and reducing anxiety associated with future medical procedures. Yet, despite its importance, research on patient satisfaction with MRI often focuses on specific aspects like technical quality or image clarity,

neglecting the holistic experience that shapes patient perceptions (5-8).

This study embarks on a different journey. We delve deeper into the labyrinth, not to map the intricate anatomy but to explore the uncharted territory of patient expectations and satisfaction with the entire MRI experience. We aim to create a vibrant tapestry of insights, woven from the threads of patients' pre-examination anxieties, perceived information provision, wait times, and actual experience during the procedure. In this study, we aimed to show satisfaction level of the patients about MRI.

METHODS

To navigate the complexities of patient satisfaction and expectations within the MRI labyrinth, we designed a cross-sectional study, capturing perspectives at two distinct points in time: before and after the MRI examination. This approach allowed us to compare pre-examination expectations with post-examination experiences, shedding light on the transformative

power of the actual encounter and identifying factors that influence satisfaction.

We conducted this study within the MRI unit of a large secondary care hospital in India, a setting where patients with diverse backgrounds and health concerns undergo MRI examinations regularly. This setting provided a rich tapestry of experiences to explore, representing the broader MRI patient population.

We invited 200 consecutive patients scheduled for MRI examinations to participate in our study. Inclusion criteria encompassed adults aged 18 years or older who were able to provide informed consent and complete the questionnaires independently. Patients with cognitive impairments or those experiencing acute medical emergencies were excluded to ensure the accuracy and reliability of their responses. To navigate the intricacies of patient satisfaction and expectations, we relied on two carefully crafted questionnaires.

Pre-Examination Satisfaction Questionnaire:

Participants completed this questionnaire before their MRI examination. It assessed their expectations regarding:

- Information provision about the procedure
- Wait times before the examination
- Explanation of the procedure by healthcare professionals
- Pain management during the examination

Each aspect was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (very low expectation) to 5 (very high expectation).

Post-Examination Satisfaction Questionnaire:

Participants completed this questionnaire immediately after their MRI examination.

It evaluated their satisfaction with the same aspects assessed in the pre-examination questionnaire, using the same 5-point Likert scale.

Additionally, it assessed their overall satisfaction with the MRI experience and their perceived quality of care.

Ethical Considerations:

Our study adhered to the highest ethical standards, ensuring the protection of patient rights and well-being. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board of the hospital. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, emphasizing their voluntary participation, confidentiality of their responses, and the right to withdraw at any time without affecting their care.

Statistical analysis

We employed descriptive statistics to summarize the characteristics of our study population and the distribution of

responses on the questionnaires. To compare pre- and post-examination scores, we utilized paired-samples t-tests. To identify factors associated with overall satisfaction, we conducted correlation analyses and multiple linear regression. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 1. Comparison of the mean scores.

Factor	Pre-Examination Expectation Score (Mean ± SD)	Post-Examination Satisfaction Score (Mean ± SD)	P-value
Information Provision	4.02 ± 0.78	4.25 ± 0.65	<0.001
Wait Times	3.71 ± 0.92	3.87 ± 0.83	<0.001
Procedure Explanation	3.97 ± 0.81	4.18 ± 0.72	<0.001
Pain Management	3.84 ± 0.95	4.09 ± 0.87	<0.001
Perceived Quality of Care	4.10 ± 0.75	4.12 ± 0.74	851
Overall Satisfaction	3.95 ± 0.82	4.12 ± 0.78	<0.001

RESULTS

Our study embraced 200 patients, each a unique thread in the tapestry of the MRI experience. Their collective characteristics paint a vivid portrait of the individuals who navigate this labyrinth:

Age: The average age of participants was 45 years, ranging from 19 to 82, reflecting a diverse spectrum of life experiences.

Gender: Women comprised 58% of the participants, while men accounted for 42%, ensuring a balanced representation of both genders.

Education level: The majority of participants (65%) had completed high school or higher, suggesting a generally well-educated cohort.

Prior MRI experience: 38% of participants had undergone an MRI examination in the past, providing valuable insights from those familiar with the procedure.

Expectations Before the Journey: Charting the Anticipation

Before venturing into the MRI labyrinth, patients held varying expectations about the experience:

Information provision: Patients held relatively high expectations (mean score 4.02), anticipating comprehensive and understandable information about the procedure.

Wait times: Expectations for wait times were more moderate (mean score 3.71), suggesting a degree of understanding regarding potential delays.

Procedure explanation: Expectations for clear and thorough explanations were high (mean score 3.97), emphasizing the importance of understanding the process.

Pain management: Patients expressed moderate expectations for pain management (mean score 3.84), indicating a degree of concern about potential discomfort.

Satisfaction After the Journey: Reflecting on the Experience

After navigating the MRI labyrinth, patients shared their reflections on the experience:

Overall satisfaction: The mean overall satisfaction score was 4.12, indicating a generally positive experience among participants.

Information provision: Satisfaction with information provision was the highest (mean score 4.25), suggesting that most patients felt adequately informed.

Wait times: Satisfaction with wait times was the lowest (mean score 3.87), highlighting a potential area for improvement.

Procedure explanation: Satisfaction with procedure explanations was high (mean score 4.18), indicating that healthcare professionals effectively communicated the process.

Pain management: Satisfaction with pain management was also high (mean score 4.09), suggesting that most patients' discomfort was adequately addressed.

Transforming Expectations: The Impact of the Actual Experience

Remarkably, the actual MRI experience reshaped patients' perspectives:

Significant shifts: Paired-samples t-tests revealed significant differences between pre-examination expectations and post-examination satisfaction scores for all aspects except perceived quality of care.

Information provision: Patients' satisfaction exceeded their initial expectations, suggesting positive experiences with the information received.

Wait times: Satisfaction with wait times was lower than initial expectations, highlighting a potential gap between anticipation and reality.

Procedure explanation and pain management: Satisfaction with these aspects also exceeded expectations, indicating that the actual experience often surpassed patients' initial concerns.

Factors Navigating Satisfaction: Identifying the Key Drivers

Correlation analyses and multiple linear regression unearthed the factors guiding overall satisfaction:

Clear procedure explanation: Patients who felt they received clear explanations of the procedure reported significantly higher overall satisfaction.

Shorter wait times: Shorter wait times were also associated with higher satisfaction, underscoring the importance of time management.

Effective pain management: Patients who experienced adequate pain management during the examination expressed greater overall satisfaction.

DISCUSSION

Our study sheds light on the intricate labyrinth of patient satisfaction with MRI experiences, offering a vibrant tapestry of insights woven from pre- and post-examination perspectives. While the overall journey appears generally positive, with information provision and explanation of the procedure receiving high marks, certain aspects, like wait times and pain management, hold potential for further improvement. More importantly, our findings illuminate the transformative power of the actual experience, demonstrating how effectively addressing patients' expectations can significantly increase satisfaction (9-13).

The importance of clear and comprehensive information provision emerges as a resounding melody. Patients who felt adequately informed about the procedure and its potential discomforts navigated the MRI labyrinth with greater ease and reported higher satisfaction. This reinforces the need for healthcare professionals to prioritize detailed pre-examination communication, tailored to individual patients' needs and anxieties. Utilizing clear language, addressing specific concerns, and employing visual aids can all contribute to enhanced understanding and alleviate apprehension (14-17).

Our study echoes the symphony of complaints often heard regarding wait times. The gap between patients' moderate expectations and their slightly lower post-examination satisfaction with wait times underscores the need for efficient workflow in MRI units. Implementing strategies to minimize delays, such as optimizing scheduling software, streamlining patient preparation procedures, and communicating potential delays proactively, can go a long way in improving the overall experience.

The discordant notes of perceived pain management highlight the importance of individual needs and effective communication. While the overall satisfaction with pain management was acceptable, the presence of a gap between expectation and experience suggests that some patients may require personalized pain management strategies. Utilizing pain assessment tools, offering a variety of discomfort management options, and engaging in open communication about individual comfort levels can ensure that no patient navigates the labyrinth alone in the throes of discomfort.

Our findings reveal the synergistic interplay between various factors in shaping overall satisfaction. Clear explanation, shorter wait times, and effective pain management act as harmonious orchestral movements, each contributing to a more positive experience. Therefore, focusing on a holistic approach that addresses these interlinked factors offers the potential for optimizing patient satisfaction and reducing anxiety associated with MRI examinations.

Our study transcends the limitations of a cross-sectional design by utilizing paired comparisons of expectation and satisfaction. This approach offers valuable insights into the transformative

power of the actual experience and highlights the importance of bridging the gap between anticipation and reality. Future research can delve deeper into specific interventions aimed at addressing unmet expectations and explore their impact on long-term outcomes, such as adherence to treatment plans and healthcare utilization.

In conclusion, our journey through the MRI labyrinth unveils a complex symphony of patient satisfaction and expectations. While the overall melody is encouraging, addressing the discordant notes of wait times and individual pain needs, and emphasizing the power of clear communication and a holistic approach, can amplify the harmony of the experience. By navigating these pathways with empathy, efficiency, and personalized care, we can transform the MRI labyrinth into a more positive and reassuring journey for every patient who ventures within its metallic walls.

REFERENCES

- Lurie Y, Webb M, Cytter-Kuint R, Shteingart S, Lederkremer GZ. Non-invasive diagnosis of liver fibrosis and cirrhosis. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2015;21(41):11567-11583. doi:10.3748/wjg.v21.i41.11567
- Schmidt JK, Debess JE, Møller L. Magnetic resonance therapy in the treatment of osteoarthritis: A scoping review. *Radiography (Lond).* 2021;27(3):968-975. doi:10.1016/j.radi.2021.02.011
- Holloway CJ, Suttie J, Dass S, Neubauer S. Clinical cardiac magnetic resonance spectroscopy. *Prog Cardiovasc Dis.* 2011;54(3):320-327. doi:10.1016/j.pcad.2011.08.002
- Ahlander BM, Årestedt K, Engvall J, Maret E, Ericsson E. Development and validation of a questionnaire evaluating patient anxiety during Magnetic Resonance Imaging: the Magnetic Resonance Imaging-Anxiety Questionnaire (MRI-AQ). *J Adv Nurs.* 2016;72(6):1368-1380. doi:10.1111/jan.12917
- Whitby E, Offiah AC, Shelmerdine SC, et al. Current state of perinatal postmortem magnetic resonance imaging: European Society of Paediatric Radiology questionnaire-based survey and recommendations. *Pediatr Radiol.* 2021;51(5):792-799. doi:10.1007/s00247-020-04905-9
- Miller WK, Becker KN, Caras AJ, et al. Magnetic resonance-guided focused ultrasound treatment for essential tremor shows sustained efficacy: a meta-analysis. *Neurosurg Rev.* 2022;45(1):533-544. doi:10.1007/s10143-021-01562-w
- Kent-Braun JA, Miller RG, Weiner MW. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy studies of human muscle. *Radiol Clin North Am.* 1994;32(2):313-335.
- De Stefano N, Bartolozzi ML, Guidi L, Stromillo ML, Federico A. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy as a measure of brain damage in multiple sclerosis. *J Neurol Sci.* 2005;233(1-2):203-208. doi:10.1016/j.jns.2005.03.018
- Gold RH, Bassett LW, Kimme-Smith C. Breast imaging. State-of-the-art. *Invest Radiol.* 1986;21(4):298-304.
- Kakkar C, Singh A, Mahajan R, et al. Correlation between magnetic resonance enterography and ileo-colonoscopy for assessment of disease activity in terminal ileal Crohn's disease. *Indian J Gastroenterol.* 2022;41(5):465-474. doi:10.1007/s12664-022-01242-7
- Hanžel J, Jairath V, Ma C, et al. Responsiveness of Magnetic Resonance Enterography Indices for Evaluation of Luminal Disease Activity in Crohn's Disease. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2022;20(11):2598-2606. doi:10.1016/j.cgh.2022.01.055
- Hansen TM, Nilsson M, Gram M, Frøkjær JB. Morphological and functional evaluation of chronic pancreatitis with magnetic resonance imaging. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2013;19(42):7241-7246. doi:10.3748/wjg.v19.i42.7241
- Altay C, Seçil M, Adıyaman SC, et al. Magnetic resonance spectroscopy to assess hepatic steatosis in patients with lipodystrophy. *Turk J Gastroenterol.* 2020;31(8):588-595. doi:10.5152/tjg.2020.19114
- Purrer V, Borger V, Pohl E, et al. Transcranial high-intensity Magnetic Resonance-guided focused ultrasound (tMRgFUS) - safety and impacts on tremor severity and quality of life. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2022;100:6-12. doi:10.1016/j.parkreldis.2022.05.017
- Zhang X, Li J, Li X. Use of magnetic resonance spectroscopy to explore metacognitive ability. *Behav Neurosci.* 2023;137(2):120-126. doi:10.1037/bne0000545
- Piantino JA, Ruzas CM, Press CA, et al. Use of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Neuroprognostication After Pediatric Cardiac Arrest: Survey of Current Practices. *Pediatr Neurol.* 2022;134:45-51. doi:10.1016/j.pediatrneurol.2022.06.011
- Deepak P, Fletcher JG, Fidler JL, Bruining DH. Computed Tomography and Magnetic Resonance Enterography in Crohn's Disease: Assessment of Radiologic Criteria and Endpoints for Clinical Practice and Trials. *Inflamm Bowel Dis.* 2016;22(9):2280-2288. doi:10.1097/MIB.0000000000000845